

**MEDIA COMMUNICATION TERMS AND THEIR SPECIFIC FEATURES
IN MODERN LINGUISTICS****Tojaliyev Akmaljon Mo'minjon o'g'li**

Fergana state university second-year student of master's degree

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Communication media is a medium or channel through which a message or information can be transmitted from a sender to the receiver. Different means through which verbal or non-verbal language is processed are understood as communication media channels that are used by students, college, university, businesses, marketers, etc to channelize communications, develop public relations and share information. Communication media is defined as means of delivering or receiving a message, information, or data. The means through which the information is passed can be in verbal or non-verbal type. There has to be a common language known by both the sender or receiver to transfer information successfully.

For example, the way a professor addresses his or her students, or the way army majors communicate with their units or the way businesses communicate with their prospects giving them hands-on experience of products or services, all use verbal or non-verbal types of communication media.

Likewise, in telecommunication, when communications take place over a distance with the help of cable, broadcasting, telegraph, or telephone, analog and digital forms of communications media channels are used to send and receive information. Hence, communication media is regarded as an essential component of all forms of communication[1].

Based on the language and methods of communication, the professional communication media is broadly divided into two types- Verbal Media & Non-verbal Media. Both of these types of communication media are used in business, marketing, advertising, publishing, journalism, science, career, education program or courses, technology, media, production, and many other sectors around the world. Let us understand these in detail:

1. Verbal Media

When the information is transmitted through words, it is known as verbal communication. Verbal communication is further divided into two types that are oral and written communication.

1. Oral Communication

Oral communication is communication through the means of speaking. It happens when one is engaged in a conversation, talking to someone on the

telephone or through video calls, interviews, presentations, meetings, debates, etc.

In any organization, people communicate orally in formal and informal situations more than in writing. It is one of the essential tools to build a relationship. A person who has polished speaking skills is bound to catch the attention of the public.

Various forms of oral communication are described below:

Face-to-face conversation:

Oral communication is best effective when it is done face-to-face. This form of communication ensures that there is no miscommunication or misunderstanding. There is an immediate response from the listener.

1.1 Telephone

Communication through the telephone is a type of oral communication that depends entirely on the voice without any physical presence. One has to have clarity on their voice and speech to ensure passing the correct information. This type of communication has more chance of miscommunication due to connection issues. Also, confusion may arise because of similar-sounding words like 'I' and 'eye.'

1.2 Presentation

A presentation is a formal type of face-to-face oral communication. Presentation is always based on a particular topic to deliver knowledge or awareness to the audience for example a film. It is the responsibility of the one who is presenting to communicate with the audience[3].

1.3 Public speech

A public speech is oral communication that can be formal or informal. In a public speech, the speaker has to address the audience. It may be for entertainment, sharing ideas, inspiring, or encouraging people. Public speech depends a lot on the public speaking skill of a person.

1.4 Interview

An interview is a formal means of oral communication that takes place for recruitment. In an interview, there could be a panel of people or a single person interviewing a candidate. It is done to assess the candidate's knowledge and personality.

1.5 Meeting

A meeting involves more than two people. There is always a head who presides over the meeting[2]. It is held for a purpose to address an issue or pass on some

crucial piece of information. It is a type of formal oral communication that is always backed by a written form of communication.

2. Written Communication

Written communication is a type of verbal communication that involves written words. It involves the passing of messages, information, or data in a written form. Generally, if used along with oral communication, it improves the credibility of the matter discussed. It is easier when people have material to read at their own expense of time. Given below are some of the forms of written communication.

1. E-mails

In an organization, e-mail is the most common means of written communication. Professionals use it to send documents, proposals, or applications to their superiors, subordinates, or clients. E-mail is the most effective way of communicating with clients or partners.

2. Proposals

A proposal from a business perspective is a written document drafted for an upcoming project or a document for a client to obtain a specific job. For example, before a company starts a campaign, one requires a written proposal to have a clear idea of the process and outcome.

3. Reports

Reports are a written document that narrates the specific function or performance of business or employees activities. It is another type of written form of formal communication. The report is essential because the employees and the stakeholders can have a clear idea about the business activities through it[4].

4. Brochures

Brochures are a written document that is an informative paper used as a template, pamphlet, or leaflet. A brochure is used by the company to help sell its product or services. It is a promotional written document used to inform the customer about the company or its product.

Menu, research paper, form, and other related mediums are used to establish links between sender and receiver of a message.

2. Non-verbal media

Non-verbal communication takes place without any exchange of words. The message is transmitted through a non-verbal platform. Given below are the types of non-verbal communication.

- Facial expression

- Gestures
- Body Language
- Proximity
- Touch
- Personal appearance
- Silence

A lot can be conveyed through the means of non-verbal communication. But it can often lead to miscommunication or misunderstanding. Hence it should always be supported by a relevant form of verbal communication if possible.

Indeed, expressions can sometimes portray countless emotions. When one is speaking on a stage, besides speaking skills, a gesture, facial expression, and body language can also help draw the public's attention.

Nowadays, when telecommunication is one of the most popular forms of communication integral to all sorts of business, news, department-based, and mass media communications, let us also understand the two forms of media that are alleviating such communications-

Different means are used for transmitting data from one source to another. These two forms of communication media are-

1. Analog

Some of the common examples of analog media are conventional radios, land-line telephones, VCRs, television transmissions, etc.

2. Digital

Common examples of digital media can be compute networking, smartphones, computer-mediated communication, e-mail, website, application, etc[5].

All in all, such communication mediums act as channels as they help in linking various sources to pass the information, message, or data. Let us now go through the types of communication media based upon the methods of communication

Examples of Popular Communication Media

Given below are some of the types of communication media;

1. Television

Television is a medium of one-way communication where a viewer is shown information in the form of audiovisual. It can be monochrome or colored. It is one of the popular sources of spreading information.

2. Radio

Radio is a communication medium where the information is passed on the audio form. The radio receives signals by modulation of electromagnetic waves. Its frequencies are said to be below those of visible light. Now, it is clear a

communication media is a medium that is used by a sender to share or transmit the information or message with a receiver. With the revolution in technology, a wide range of mediums is incorporated under verbal and non-verbal media channels with a common goal to ease down the tasks of sharing messages and optimizing the impact of the message in getting favorable outcomes from the target audiences.

There are some examples for media communication[6].

Anchorage – how meaning is fixed, as in how a caption fixes the meaning of a picture

Archetype – A universal type or model of character that is found in many different texts, e.g. ingenue, anti-hero, wise old woman, hero-as-lover, hero-as-warrior, shadow trickster, mentor, loyal friend, temptress

Audience – viewers, listeners and readers of a media text. A lot of media studies is concerned with how audience use texts and the effects a text may have on them. Also identified in demographic socio-economic categories.

Binary Opposites – the way opposites are used to create interest in media texts, such as good/bad, coward/hero, youth/age, black/white. By Barthes and Levi-Strauss who also noticed another important feature of these ‘binary opposites’: that one side of the binary pair is always seen by a particular society or culture as more valued over the other.

Catharsis – the idea that violent and and sexual content in media texts serves the function of releasing ‘pent up’ tension aggression/desire in audiences.

Censorship – Control over the content of a media text – sometimes by the government, but usually by a regulatory body like the British Board of Film censors.

CGI – Computer Generated Imagery, Refers to the (usually) 3-D effects that enhance all kinds of still and moving images, from text effects, to digital snow or fire, to the generation of entire landscapes

Code – a sign or convention through which the media communicates meaning to us because we have learned to read it. Technical codes – all to do with the way a text is technically constructed – camera angles, framing, typography, lighting etc. Visual codes – codes that are decoded on a mainly connotational level – things that draw on our experience and understanding of other media texts, this includes Iconography – which is concerned with the use of visual images and how they trigger the audiences expectations of a particular genre, such as a knife in slasher horror films.

Consumer – purchaser, listener, viewer or reader of media products.

Context – time, place or mindset in which we consume media products[7].

Conventions – the widely recognised way of doing things in particular genre.

Convergence – The way in which technologies and institutions come together in order to create something new. Cinema is the result of the convergence of photography, moving pictures (the kinoscope, zoetrope etc), and sound. The iPad represents the convergence of books, TV, maps, the internet and the mobile phone.

Demographics – Factual characteristics of a population sample, e.g. age, gender, race, nationality, income, disability, education

Denotation – the everyday or common sense meaning of a sign. Connotation – the secondary meaning that a sign carries in addition to its everyday meaning.

Diegetic Sound – Sound whose source is visible on the screen
Non Diegetic sound – Sound effects, music or narration which is added afterwards

Enigma – A question in a text that is not immediately answered and creates interest for the audience – a puzzle that the audience has to solve.

Feminism – the struggle by women to obtain equal rights in society

Gaze – the idea that the way we look at something, and the way somebody looks at you, is structured by the way we view the world. Feminist Laura Mulvey suggests that looking involves power, specifically the look of men at women, implying that men have power over women.

Genre – the type or category of a media text, according to its form, style and content.

Hegemony – Traditionally this describes the predominance of one social class over another, in media terms this is how the controllers of the media may on the one hand use the media to pursue their own political interest, but on the other hand the media is a place where people who are critical of the establishment can air their views.

Hypodermic Needle Theory – the idea that the media can ‘inject’ ideas and messages straight into the passive audience. This passive audience is immediately affected by these messages. Used in advertising and propoganda, led to moral panics about effect of violent video and computer games.

Ideology – A set of ideas or beliefs which are held to be acceptable by the creators of the media text, maybe in line with those of the dominant ruling social groups in society, or alternative ideologies such as feminist ideology.

Indexical sign – a sign which has a direct relationship with something it signifies, such as smoke signifies fire.

Image – a visual representation of something[7].

Institutions – The organisations which produce and control media texts such as the BBC, AOL Time Warner, News International.

Intertextuality – the idea that within popular culture producers borrow other texts to create interest to the audience who like to share the ‘in’ joke. Used a lot in the Simpsons.

Media language – the means by which the media communicates to us and the forms and conventions by which it does so.

Media Platform – nothing to do with trains, this refers to the different ways that media content is delivered, mainly via TV, laptop, tablet, smartphone, cinema, video/computer game, printed page etc. for instance the BBC delivers content via TV, laptop and mobile device, and also through printed publications. Most media organisations deliver their content via a multitude of platforms.

Media product – a text that has been designed to be consumed by an audience. E.G a film, radio show, newspaper etc.

Media text – see above. N.B Text usually means a piece of writing

Mise en Scene – literally ‘what’s in the shot’ everything that appears on the screen in a single frame and how this helps the audience to decode what’s going on.

Mode of Address – The way a media product ‘speaks’ to it’s audience. In order to communicate, a producer of any text must make some assumptions about an intended audience; reflections of such assumptions may be discerned in the text (advertisements offer particularly clear examples of this).

Montage – putting together of visual images to form a sequence. Made famous by Russian film maker Eisenstein in his famous film Battleship Potemkin[8].

Moral Panic – is the intensity of feeling stirred up by the media about an issue that appears to threaten the social order, such as against Muslims after 9/11, or against immigrants, or against ‘video nasties’ following the Jamie Bulger murder.

Multi-media – computer technology that allows text, sound, graphic and video images to be combined into one programme.

Myth – a complex idea by Roland Barthes that myth is a second order signifying system ie when a sign becomes the signifier of a new sign (*2nd years only this one!*)

Narrative code – The way a story is put together within a text, traditionally equilibrium- disequilibrium, new equilibrium, but some text are fractured or non liner, eg Pulp Fiction.

News values – factors that influence whether a story will be picked for coverage.

Non-verbal communication – communication between people other than by speech.

Ownership – who produces and distributes the media texts – and whose interest it is.

Patriarchy – The structural, systematic and historical domination and exploitation of women.

Popular Culture – the study of cultural artefacts of the mass media such as cinema, TV, advertising.

Post Modernism – Anything that challenges the traditional way of doing things, rejecting boundaries between high and low forms of art, rejecting rigid genre distinctions, emphasizing pastiche, parody, intertextuality, irony, and playfulness. Postmodernism favours reflexivity and self-consciousness, fragmentation and discontinuity (especially in narrative structures), ambiguity, simultaneity, and an emphasis on the destructured, decentered, dehumanized subjects! This is tricky!

Preferred Reading – the interpretation of a media product that was intended by the maker or which is dictated by the ideology of the society in which it is viewed. Oppositional Reading – an interpretation of a text by a reader whose social position puts them into direct conflict with its preferred reading. Negotiated Reading – the ‘compromise’ that is reached between the preferred reading offered by a text and the reader’s own assumptions and interpretations

Propaganda – the way ruling classes use the mass media to control or alter the attitudes of others[9].

Reader – a member of the audience, someone who is actively responding to the text.

Regulation – bodies whose job it is to see that media texts are not seen by the wrong audience (eg British Board of Film Censors) or are fair and honest (EG Advertising Standards Association)

Representation – The way in which the media ‘re-presents’ the world around us in the form of signs and codes for audiences to read.

SFX – special effects or devices to create visual illusions.

Shot – single image taken by a camera.

Sign – a word or image that is used to represent an object or idea.

Signifier/Signified – the ‘thing’ that conveys the meaning, and the meaning conveyed. EG a red rose is a signifier, the signified is love (or the Labour Party!)

Sound Effects – additional sounds other than dialogue or music, designed to add realism or atmosphere[10].

Stereotype – representation of people or groups of people by a few characteristics eg hoodies, blondes

Still – static image.

Sub-genre – a genre within a genre.

Two Step Flow theory – the idea that ideas flow from mass media to opinion leaders, and from them to a wider population.

Uses and Gratifications – ideas about how people use the media and what gratification they get from it. It assumes that members of the audience are not passive but take an active role in interpreting and integrating media into their own lives.

References:

1. Averbux K. Y. Obshaya teoriya termina. Ivanovo: Ivanovskiy gosudarstvenniy universitet, 2004. S. 52.
2. Vinogradov, V. V. O yazike xudojestvennoy literaturi [Tekst] / V. V. Vinogradov. - M.: Goslitizdat, 1959.S.149.
3. Vinokur, G. O. O nekotoryx yavleniyax slovoobrazovaniya v russkoy texnicheskoy terminologii [Tekst] / V. A. Tatarinov. Istoriya otechestvennogo terminovedeniya. Klassiki terminovedeniya: Ocherk i xrestomatiya. - M.: Moskovskiy Litsey, 1994.S.257
4. Grinev, S. V. Vvedeniye v terminovedeniye [Tekst] / S. V. Grinev. - M.: Moskovskiy Litsey, 1993. S.33, 54
5. Drozdova, T. V. Konsepti kak osnova klyuchevix ponyatiy terminologii [Tekst] / T. V. Drozdova // Konseptualniy analiz yazika: sovremenniye napravleniya issledovaniya: sb. nauch. tr. / RAN. In-t yazikoznaniya; Min-vo obraz, i nauki RF. TGU im. R.G. Derjavina; Redkol.: Kubryakova YE. S. (otv. red.), Pozdnyakova YE. M. (zam. otv. red.) i dr. - M.-Kaluga: IP Koshelev A. B. (izdatelstvo «Eydos»), 2007.S.139
6. Lotte, D. S. Uporyadocheniye texnicheskoy terminologii // B. A. Tatarinov. Istoriya otechestvennogo terminovedeniya. Klassiki terminovedeniya: Ocherk i xrestomatiya. - M.: Moskovskiy Litsey, 1994.S.74
7. Pazilova N. "EFFECTIVE WAYS OF TEACHING AND EXPANDING VOCABULARY". ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions. VOLUME 2, ISSUE 5, MAY-2021.
8. Pazilova N. "EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING WRITING (THE USE

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9. OF "CHARACTER WHEEL" METHOD)". EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH. Volume 1, Issue 2. Part 2 May 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4904069>
10. Pazilova N. "O'rganilayotgan til stilistikasi fanidan elektron qo'llanma"- "Электрон ўқув қўлланма. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Адлия вазирлиги ҳузуридаги интеллектуал мулк агентлиги. №ДГУ 14247. 17.12.2021.
11. Pazilova N. "THE INVESTIGATION OF SYNTACTICAL EXPRESSIVE MEANS AND STYLISTIC DEVICES IN MODERN ENGLISH AND UZBEK". International Journal of Research in commerce, IT, Engineering and Social Sciences. VOLUME 16, Issue 01. January 2022.
12. Qodirova Fotima Xamidjonovna, Pazilova Nasibaxon Muhammadqosimovna. "SPECIFIC FEATURES AND STRUCTURAL PATTERNS OF IDIOMS IN MODERN ENGLISH" International journal of Social Sciences & Interdisciplinary research. Volume 11, Issue 01. January 2022.
13. Pazilova Nasibaxon Muhammadqosimovna, Usmonova Dona Satvoldiyevna. "BENEFITS OF INTERACTIVE WHITEBOARDS FOR TEACHERS AND STUDENTS". Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. Volume 7. April 2022.